

Please reference this source as:

Ulrich Herb (2019). Instructions for qualitative interviews on the qualitative perception of scientific publications.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.3482888

<https://zenodo.org/record/3482888>

Background

This interview is part of the visOA project: "Making Open Access publications visible in the holdings of a library ". The topic of the survey will be the qualitative perceptions of scientific literature.

In preparation for this survey, a literature study on the qualitative evaluation of scientific documents was conducted. The guideline for the following interview was developed from this study. In order to check to what extent the criteria identified in the literature study are appropriate to the scientific context of visOA, we will conduct an interview in which I will ask you what constitutes the quality of a scientific publication for you. The results of the guided interviews will in turn help to set up a broader online survey on the quality of scientific publications.

In order to facilitate the evaluation of your interview, I would ask you to agree to record our conversation. The results of the evaluation may be used in a scientific publication. The evaluation is anonymous and will take the form of a short transcript; there will be no way of assigning your information to your person.

Consent

I hereby confirm that I agree to the recording of the guided interview and its evaluation under the condition of complete anonymisation.

Saarbrücken, 09.05.2018

Interview

Personal Information

- Name
- Academic Title
- Position
- Age
- Gender
- Subject / Research focus
- Total number of publications
- Number of publications since 2013
- Number of Open Access publications since 2013

Guided Interview

- 1. How do you define quality?**
- 2. What criteria do you use to assess the quality of scientific articles?**
- 3. Which quantitative criteria do you use to assess the quality of scientific articles?**
- 4. Which (qualitative) criteria do you use to assess the quality of scientific articles?**
- 5. Which formal criteria do you use to assess the quality of scientific articles?**
6. What role do (empirical) methods play?
7. What role do the statistical methods used play?
8. What role do research designs play?
9. What is the role of data availability?
- 10. How do you rate the quality of Open Access and Closed Access?**
- 11. Which of the criteria you have mentioned so far are crucial for the assessment of Open Access and Closed Access?**